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SOCIAL HIERARCHY OF EARLY MEDIEVAL CENTRAL ASIAN SOCIETY IN IMAGES OF FUNERAL RITUAL SCENES

Malika S. Tukhtayeva¹

Khurliman K. Baymuratova¹

¹*National Centre of Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences
(Tashkent, Uzbekistan)*

Malika S. Tukhtayeva

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1456-1573>

Khurliman K. Baymuratova

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3891-3083>

СОЦИАЛЬНАЯ ИЕРАРХИЯ РАННЕСРЕДНЕВЕКОВОГО СРЕДНЕАЗИАТСКОГО ОБЩЕСТВА В ИЗОБРАЖЕНИЯХ СЦЕН ПОХОРОННОГО РИТУАЛА

Малика С. Тухтаева¹

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1456-1573>

Хурлиман К. Баймуратова¹

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3891-3083>

¹*Национальный центр археологии Академии наук
(Ташкент, Узбекистан)*

Abstract

This article explores the representation of social hierarchy in early medieval Central Asian society through visual depictions of funerary rituals. Drawing on archaeological findings and artistic evidence – particularly painted ossuaries from Tok-Kala and mural paintings from Penjikent – the study reveals how burial customs reflect spiritual beliefs and social stratification. The Tok-Kala ossuaries depict the deceased in a central, elevated position, surrounded by priests, relatives, and lower-class corpse handlers, highlighting a clear tripartite social order. Similarly, the Penjikent wall paintings portray a nobleman placed inside a ceremonial structure, accompanied by female mourners, ritual specialists, loyal warriors, and divine figures. The spatial arrangement and gestures of the participants indicate their respective social statuses. Acts of self-torture among mourners, especially warriors, emphasize themes of loyalty and sacrifice. The article argues that, while death might suggest existential equality, these artistic compositions affirm that social distinctions endured even in death. Through the analysis of funerary art, the study provides valuable insight into the religious practices, cultural values, and hierarchical structures of early medieval Central Asian societies.

Аннотация

В этой статье рассматривается представление социальной иерархии в раннесредневековом среднеазиатском обществе посредством визуальных изображений погребальных ритуалов. Опираясь на археологические находки и художественные свидетельства – в частности, расписные оссуарии из Ток-Калы и настенные росписи из Пенджикента – исследование показывает, как погребальные обычаи отражают духовные верования и социальную стратификацию. Оссуарии Ток-Калы изображают покойного в центральном, возвышенном положении, окруженного жрецами, родственниками и обработчиками трупов низшего класса, что подчеркивает четкий трехсторонний социальный порядок. Аналогичным образом, настенные росписи Пенджикента изображают знатного человека, помещенного внутрь церемониальной структуры, в сопровождении женщин-плакальщиц, специалистов по ритуалам, верных воинов и божественных фигур. Пространственное расположение и жесты участников указывают на их соответствующие социальные статусы. Акты самоистязания среди плакальщиков, особенно воинов, подчеркивают темы верности и жертвенности. В статье утверждается, что, хотя смерть может предполагать экзистенциальное равенство, эти художественные композиции подтверждают, что социальные различия сохраняются даже в смерти. Благодаря анализу погребального искусства исследование дает ценную информацию о религиозных обрядах, культурных ценностях и иерархических структурах раннесредневековых обществ Центральной Азии.

Keywords: Funerary rituals, social hierarchy, Ossuary, Zoroastrianism, Tok-Kala, Penjikent, Mourning, Self-torture, Visual representation, early medieval Central Asia.

Ключевые слова: Погребальные ритуалы, социальная иерархия, оссуарий, зороастризм, Ток-Кала, Пенджикент, траур, самоистязание, визуальное представление, раннесредневековая Центральная Азия

INTRODUCTION

The burial rituals of early medieval Central Asian society are extensively studied in modern scholarship

through written sources and archaeological discoveries from the late 19th to the early 21st centuries. Certain works of fine art also serve as visual evidence of unique

funerary traditions. Burial rites constitute a crucial source for understanding the spiritual culture of past societies. During the early Middle Ages, the ossuary burial rite, aligned with Zoroastrian tradition, was widespread in Central Asia. This practice was accompanied by distinct funerary structures, including *kata* (a closed chamber for temporarily storing the deceased before being transferred to the *dakhma*), *dakhma* (a structure where the deceased's remains were cleansed of flesh), and *naus* (a mausoleum for storing ossuaries). These funerary structures have been discovered across various locations in Central Asia.

The ossuary burial custom originated in Khorezm during antiquity and gradually spread to other regions of Central Asia. The form and design of ossuaries varied significantly. Some Sogdian and Khorezmian ossuaries feature depictions of funeral rites or scenes of the afterlife. These images incorporate Zoroastrian motifs but also depict ritual elements, such as mourning and self-torture, which are prohibited in orthodox Zoroastrianism (Gudkova 91; Goryacheva 118–119; Grenet 129–146). One notable example is an ossuary from Tok-Kala (Khorezm), which is uniquely decorated with polychrome painting, a rare feature among such artifacts.

METHODS

Mourning scenes were closely associated with funerary rites, commemoration of the dead, and ancestral worship. The mourning scene is a timeless artistic theme that expresses human grief for the departed. In early medieval Central Asia, this theme frequently appeared in visual art, particularly in representations of processions of the living and the deceased. Social status was often indicated in these depictions. Among the most remarkable examples are the painted ossuaries from the Tok-Kala settlement in Khorezm. Scholars highlight their significance, noting that the paintings “allow us to study the experiences of those cultural forms that, due to rapid evolution, disappeared or transformed in other areas” (Inostrantsev 286). These artifacts provide archaeologists and art historians with valuable insights into local cultural traditions, artistic styles, and funerary practices.

The ossuaries from Tok-Kala, now housed in the Savitsky State Museum of Karakalpakstan, feature intricate painted compositions (Fig. 1). The painting covers both the front side and lid of the ossuary, forming a unified visual narrative divided into an upper (lid) and lower (body) section. The central figure is the deceased, depicted lying on a bed with a headboard, clad in a long white caftan and a high headdress an emblem of high social status. L. Evtyukhova (Yevtyukhova 104) describes similar headdresses, resembling truncated cones, as indicators of high rank among the ancient Turks. Flanking the deceased, figures with raised hands are depicted, possibly engaging in acts of mourning, such as striking themselves and tearing their hair in grief. Similar gestures appear in the upper section of the painting, where groups of mourners mirror these actions (Tukhtayeva 32–44). The mourners frame the entire composition, reinforcing the emotional intensity of the scene. The artwork integrates domestic and mythological elements, offering insight into local funerary customs and belief systems.

The memorial procession depicted on these ossuaries seemingly reflects the tripartite division of feudal society: the clergy (priest and mourners), the nobility (the deceased and their relatives), and the lower class, which included the ossuary bearers. Religious and secular figures are positioned in distinct spatial arrangements, emphasizing their social hierarchy (Fig. 2). The deceased occupies the central position, likely indicating high social status. A priest, positioned at the head of the deceased, appears to be performing a ritual or reciting prayers for the safe passage of the soul. Relatives of the deceased surround the figure, while at the lowest tier, smaller-scale representations of *nassassalars* (corpse handlers) highlight their lower social standing. The mourners, engaging in self-torture, serve as a poignant reminder of the transience of life.

RESULTS

The imagery of the funeral procession conveys not only grief but also a reflection on social structures. While death may symbolize an existential equality, the visual composition underscores the persistence of social distinctions even in funerary rites. The elaborate execution of this ossuary suggests that the deceased held a distinguished position within their community. The arrangement of male and female mourners in the same row, depicted at an equal scale, implies a degree of social parity between genders. This funerary monument functions as both a representation of mourning customs and a didactic guide on proper funerary procedures. Within this framework, ritualistic self-torture and symbolic elements gain particular significance. Ultimately, while the scene conveys themes of mortality and existential equality, it simultaneously affirms the enduring nature of social stratification, as evident in the cost and complexity of such an elaborate burial artifact.

The “Mourning” scene from the Penjikent wall paintings provides a visual representation of social stratification and ritual hierarchy in a pre-Islamic Sogdian funeral. By analyzing the placement, actions, and attributes of the figures, we can identify the hierarchical structure embedded in the composition (Fig. 3).

1. The Central Figure – The Deceased

The deceased nobleman is positioned inside a *ki-osk*-like structure, elevated and separated from the mourners. His placement within an architectural framework underscores his high social status. His young, beardless face and loose hair may indicate aristocratic lineage or his role as a young warrior, as these features were often associated with nobility in Sogdian culture.

Hierarchy Level: The Highest (Elite / Aristocracy)

2. The Women behind the Arches (Close Female Mourners)

The women positioned within the same structure as the deceased, striking themselves on the head, likely represent close female relatives, such as wives or concubines. Their act of self-inflicted pain signifies intense grief and loyalty. Their placement behind the arches emphasizes their social proximity to the deceased in life and death.

Hierarchy Level: Upper Class (Close Family or Concubines of the Deceased)

3. The Torch Bearers and Vessel Holder

Three figures in white, two holding torches and one carrying a jug-like vessel, stand prominently before

the structure. The torches may symbolize ritual purification or fire-worship practices, potentially linked to Zoroastrian rites. The vessel-holder might be performing a libation ritual, an offering to deities or spirits. Their role in overseeing funeral rites suggests they are priests or high-status attendants.

Hierarchy Level: Religious Functionaries or Ritual Specialists (Priests, Temple Attendants)

4. The Mourning Group in the Foreground (Men & Women Engaging in Self-Torture)

In front of the kiosk, four men and one woman engage in self-mutilation, including cutting themselves and severing their earlobes with knives. Their distinctly Turkic features may indicate that they were warriors or retainers of the deceased, performing a warrior's mourning ritual. Self-mutilation was a sign of loyalty and grief, possibly signifying their role as bodyguards, companions, or high-ranking military subordinates. The presence of a woman among them suggests that she might be a professional mourner or a court-affiliated ritual participant.

Hierarchy Level: High-Ranking Warriors & Professional Mourners

5. The Three Female Deities

The largest deity, depicted with four arms and a radiant crown, is likely associated with death, the after-life, or the protection of the soul. The presence of divine figures reinforces the sacred nature of the event, indicating that the deceased was connected to divine favor or religious status. These deities exist outside the human social hierarchy, signifying the cosmic or religious significance of the funeral.

Hierarchy Level: Divine Beings (Beyond the Human Hierarchy, Supreme Forces in the Ritual Context)

Hierarchical Ranking of Figures in the Scene

Rank

Figures in the Scene

Status/Function

1 The Deceased (inside the kiosk)

Elite Aristocrat or Noble Warrior

2 Women behind the arches

Close Relatives (Wives, Concubines, or Female Mourners of High Rank)

3 Torch Bearers & Vessel Holder

Priests or Ritual Specialists

4 Men & Woman in the Foreground (Self-Mutilation Group)

Warriors, Bodyguards, or Professional Mourners

5 Three Female Deities

Divine Entities (Outside Human Hierarchy, Sacred Participants in the Ritual)

DISCUSSION

The funeral scene at Penjikent reflects a distinct social hierarchy, with the deceased nobleman at the apex, surrounded by his inner circle of mourners, ritual specialists, and loyal warriors. The inclusion of divine figures elevates the ritual beyond a private mourning event, suggesting its significance at a communal or state level. The depiction of self-torture emphasizes the

warrior culture of extreme loyalty, reinforcing the role of personal sacrifice in Sogdian funerary traditions.

The custom of self-torture during funerary ceremonies in pre-Islamic Central Asia is well-documented in the Penjikent wall paintings. In Temple II, on the central part of the southern wall of the main hall, a painting depicting a funeral rite the "Mourning" scene was discovered. The preserved portion of the composition illustrates the funeral ritual. The deceased is placed in a dome-like structure (pavilion, kiosk), the visible part of which consists of a two-tiered arcature (Belenitskiy 33–35). Within this structure, behind the spans of arches, the figure of the deceased appears with a youthful, beardless face and loose hair. Behind him, women are depicted striking themselves on the head. In the foreground, a large group of mourners is present. Three figures dressed in white stand near the structure. Two hold identical objects with thick, twisted handles, likely torches, while the third carries a handle less jug-shaped vessel with a high neck. Below them, another row of participants is visible, consisting of four men and one woman. The men, depicted with distinctly Turkic facial features, stand in pairs facing each other. The poor condition of this part of the painting suggests that additional participants might have been present (Fig. 4). The grief of these individuals is conveyed with great expressiveness through their poses, loose hair, and acts of self-torture. Many figures display traces of scratches and cuts on their exposed bodies and faces (Fig. 5). Particularly striking are two male figures in identical poses, depicted at the moment they cut their earlobes with long knives (Belenitskiy 81). To the left of the mourning group, three female deities are present. The largest, a four-armed figure with a large radiant crown, dominates the composition (Fig. 6). According to A.M. Belenitsky, this scene represents the burial of a noble aristocrat (Belenitskiy 76–82; Shkoda 82–88).

CONCLUSION

Works of art serve as valuable sources for understanding social differences and inequalities, reflecting the unequal distribution of social, political, and symbolic power. This early medieval painting highlights the deep connection between individuals and the natural world, as well as their dependence on it. The images function not only as decorative elements or religious instruments of moral education but also as artifacts of profound social change. This article examines how social hierarchy is represented in visual depictions of funerary rituals. In the medieval worldview, death was not merely the end of life but the beginning of an after-life. Painted ossuaries were accessible only to those occupying privileged positions in society. The analysis of mourning scenes in visual art suggests that social inequality persisted in abstract form even after death. In depicting memorial processions, the artist adhered to the tripartite model of feudal society, consisting of the clergy, the nobility, and the third estate, including the Nassassalars. Religious and secular figures are clearly separated and represented in distinct spatial planes, reinforcing their social stratification.

Pic. 1

Pic. 2

Таблица XX. Объект II, притеснен В

Pic. 3

Таблица XIX. Объект II, притеснен В. Схема центральной части композиции

Pic. 4

Таблица XXIII. Объект II, притеснен В. Деталь

Pic. 5

Таблица XXII. Объект II, притеснен В. В. Деталь

Pic. 6

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Caption for the pictures

1. Fig. 1. The ossuaries from Tok-Kala (Khorezm) (M. Tokhtaeva's pace)
2. Fig. 2. Drawing of an ossuary (Shukurov, 1977).

3. Fig. 3. Panjikent, Temple II. The central part of the southern wall of the main hall. Painting – scene of “Lamentation”. (by A.M.Belenitsky)
4. Fig. 4. The funeral scene at Panjikent, Object II, Section B
5. Fig. 5. Panjikent, Object II, Section B. Detail.
6. Fig. 6. Panjikent, Object II, Section B. Detail.